

CHALLENGES IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract. This article investigates global practices in teaching young learners. The aim in this article is to identify the challenges faced by teachers of primary English both globally, across the total number of countries involved in the study. Our aim is to portray overall trends but also to explore local variation and possible reasons for this variation.

Key words: teaching English, primary students, to communicate, learning, method, situation, teaching, primary, ability, development, teaching, motivation, challenges, problems, methods, suggests.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА ЮНЫМ УЧЕНИКАМ

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется мировая практика обучения младших школьников. Целью данной статьи является определение проблем, с которыми сталкиваются учителя начального английского языка во всем мире и во всем количестве стран, участвовавших в исследовании. Наша цель — отобразить общие тенденции, а также изучить местные различия и возможные причины этих различий.

Ключевые слова: преподавание английского языка, учащиеся начальных классов, общение, обучение, метод, ситуация, обучение, начальное образование, способности, развитие, обучение, мотивация, задачи, проблемы, методы, подсказки.

In the last few centuries, English has become a lingua franca which makes it one of the most important languages and is learnt in all over the world. Today's globalization era also tends to force people to be able to understand English well since it is used in all sectors such as academic, business, politics, career, etc.

In that case, many people consider that an early start in learning English become a priority. An early start is strongly connected with age, it can be said that early start has the same meaning as the age of the child. According to some scientist, age is an important factor that plays an important role in learning process of a language. Many people believe that the sooner we learn a language is the better. As the result, children start to learn English at younger and younger ages nowadays. Primary students, who are commonly referred to as young learners, are now in the centre of education and are given much more attention.

Teaching English to young children is a rewarding but challenging task. It requires patience, organization, and full dedication to providing a fun and stimulating learning environment for your little students. This type of teaching can be especially effective if you are able to connect with and devote your undivided to each child.

While teaching can sometimes be demanding, the rewards that come from seeing children grow and learn are undeniable, and sometime exhilarating.

Teachers may therefore find themselves teaching English either without adequate training in teaching young learners in general or in teaching English to young learners in particular. The situation is especially acute in poor or rural areas.

Linked to policies about pedagogy is the issue of resources. In some countries such as South Korea (Butler, 2004) and Malaysia (Pandian, 2003) textbooks are prescribed. In other countries, teachers can choose from government-approved books, for example, in Singapore (Mee, 2003) and in China (G. Hu, 2005). Given the global prevalence of early English learning, it is a matter of concern that in many countries, appropriate books are either not available (Hoque, 2009; Y. Hu, 2007; Mathew & Pani, 2009) or are not used in the classroom.

In many parts of the world, large classes are a common challenge, causing teachers to believe it is difficult or impossible to introduce learner-centered teaching because, for example, they cannot closely monitor students' language use (Li, 1998) or use pair work and group work. A related issue is the problem of control and discipline Carless (2004) argues that the noise produced during speaking activities can be problematic when the local preference is for quiet and orderly classrooms.

Another problem in teaching younger schoolchildren a foreign language is motivation and understanding what a foreign language is needed for in later life. Students' lack of motivation may be caused by a lack of support from their parents. The following problem follows from it — this is inattention and restlessness in the classroom. Memory Songbatumis spoke in detail about her experience when she once caught a student who did not bring any books to school due to forgetfulness. In contrast, other students intentionally left their books on the classroom table. Memory Songbatumis believes that such things would not have happened if the parents of students controlled the education of their children at home. The students will be highly motivated once they know what they are expected to be able to do after learning certain materials as well as the things they could relate to the material are. According to L. A. Tsyban, primary school students are inattentive due to their period of development, so children are distracted, cannot concentrate on the educational material and stop listening to the teacher. At the same time, new, unexpected and vivid material is remembered faster and easier. Many teachers take advantage of this and use more visual material in their work. At the same time, it can be beautiful, colorful and interesting, and students may miss significant and serious details of the submitted material.

The next problem is shyness. The first obstacle to learning a foreign language is shyness. Students who are just starting to learn a foreign language will be afraid: "I won't be able to speak this language correctly; I won't be able to learn this language."

Additionally, one of the main obstacles to learning English is the lack of time. No matter how well organized and effective the lesson is, if the student does not apply what he has learned in practice, he will quickly forget what he learned during the lesson. Therefore, it is right to have enough time to develop the student's English language skills. According to A. O. Pirozhkova, younger schoolchildren perceive symbolic and schematic images worse and visual material is better. Many trainers in the field of education know that in the process of learning, children need a frequent change of events and activities; otherwise they get tired pretty quickly. Based on my experience, the best way to solve this problem is first to find out their own needs and weaknesses.

In conclusion, I would like to note that these problems arise for every foreign language teacher to a greater or lesser extent. There are many difficulties in learning English, which has become a world language. Nevertheless, any teacher who finds the key to these problems thinks about the best ways to learn a foreign language and can eliminate any obstacles using effective,

advanced technologies. Liton, a scientist from Europe, noted in his research that both teachers and students face problems in mastering English. Teaching a foreign language at school requires a high level of professional skill, love for children, as well as efforts and ability to present the material so that students successfully assimilate it and show interest in the subject. This, of course, can be achieved with some effort, and, as practice shows, success depends not so much on experience as on the enthusiasm, energy and interest of the teacher. In addition, the use of ICT in teaching foreign languages plays an important role. Shyness of the student, lack of time, textbooks with difficult tasks, etc. – it was found that such problems have a negative impact on the level of mastery of the English language of the student. In general, in order to overcome the obstacles that students face when teaching them English, the teacher must constantly improve their professional skills.

Most Uzbekistan schools choose English either as the first or the second compulsory foreign language. If students start learning English in primary school, they usually have the same specialist teacher from the 1st grade until they are in the 5th grade, when they finish secondary school first level. During primary and secondary school years, foreign language studies are allotted 2, maximum 3 hours a week for expanding or improving linguistic competencies.

There are many reasons for starting with the teaching of English at an early age. As the concept “teaching English to young learners” suggests, age plays a crucial role in what we teach and how we teach it, since a young learner class is different from an adult and/or a teenager class in terms of the learners’ language learning needs, the language 2 competences emphasized, and the cognitive skills addressed. Specialists have in mind and expect that gaining some additional years for the learning of English as the most important international language will take learners to higher levels of competence in its use. Language researchers and educationalists point out that the younger children are the less difficulty they have with the second language acquisition because of the greater plasticity of their neuronal circuits. Early learning of a second language is also hoped to pave the way for more intercultural understanding and facilitate the later learning of a third or fourth language. Studies have proved that learning English at an early age helps students grasp their mother tongue better, simultaneously enabling them to acquire remarkable proficiency in their second language. The implementation of English teaching in kindergarten may also become a useful means for the younger generation to understand a deeper knowledge of religions and cultures in the world.

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